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AGEING AND USE OF COMPLEX PRODUCT INTERFACES

Gudur Raghavendra Reddy*, Alethea Blackler*, Vesna Popovic*, and Doug Mahar **,

* School of Design, Queensland University of Technology

**School of Psychology and Counselling, Queensland University of Technology
Brisbane, Queensland, Australia

{r.gudur;a.blackler;v.popovic;d.mahar}@qut.edu.au

ABSTRACT

This paper presents an experiment designed to investigate if redundancy in an interface has any impact on the use of complex interfaces by older people and people with low prior-experience with technology. The important findings of this study were that older people (65+ years) completed the tasks on the Words only based interface faster than on Redundant (text and symbols) interface. The rest of the participants completed tasks significantly faster on the Redundant interface. From a cognitive processing perspective, sustained attention (one of the functions of Central Executive) has emerged as one of the important factors in completing tasks on complex interfaces faster and with fewer of errors.

Keywords: *Intuitive interaction, usability, ageing, interface design.*

INTRODUCTION

Older people have difficulties using contemporary consumer products with complex interfaces and extensive functionality. They are also less likely to use complex devices intuitively and are slower when compared to younger people (Blackler, Popovic, & Mahar, 2009; Lewis, Langdon, & Clarkson, 2008). Not being able to use contemporary technologies like computers, the Internet and ever increasing self-care medical devices puts the older population at a disadvantage in terms of their ability to live and function independently. Although current generation graphics-intensive interfaces appear to be intuitive to use for most people, some studies have found that older users have difficulty assessing the functionality of interfaces that use graphics

extensively (Gould & Schaefer, 2005). It is also observed that graphics based interfaces can increase extraneous cognitive load and can have an adverse impacts on learning of interface functionality (Feinberg & Murphy, 2000; Sweller, 1994).

An experiment was designed to investigate if words only, symbols only or redundancy (text and symbols) in an interface has any impact on use of complex interfaces in older people and people with low prior-experience with technology. A virtual product with three variations of an interface was used in this experiment. The outcomes of this experiment will be discussed from both interface design and cognitive processing perspectives, along with their contribution to developing appropriate strategies to design interfaces that are intuitive to use for older people.

INTUTIVE INTERACTION

Intuitive use of product interfaces involves unconscious use of user’s prior-knowledge related to the product in use. In other words, the user is familiar (based on their earlier encounter with similar products) with different features and functions of the product (Blackler, Popovic, & Mahar, 2010; Hurtienne, Weber, & Blessing, 2008). Intuitive use of an interface can be recognised by the following characteristics (Blackler, 2008):

- (1) It is fast and effortless*
- (2) It is generally non-conscious and does not involve conscious reasoning or analysis and*
- (3) It is based on relevant past experiences.*

DESIGNING FOR OLDER ADULTS

Many older adults have difficulties in using complex contemporary product interfaces. According to

Docampo Rama (2001) at least three factors contribute to this difficulty:

- (1) Complexity of user interface,*
- (2) Age-related changes in cognitive abilities, and*
- (3) Generation-related differences in experience with technology.*

However, a more recent study on using technological products effectively, did not find any significant generation-related differences in older people (Lewis, Langdon, & Clarkson, 2007). On the other hand, studies confirm that age related decline in cognitive functioning affects the speed and accuracy of using complex technological products (Lewis, et al., 2008; Reddy, Blackler, Popovic, & Mahar, 2010). Age-related decline in cognitive and sensory-motor function occurs slowly albeit at varied intensities from individual to individual. It is possible to have two individuals share the same chronological age, but have different rates of age-related cognitive and psychological decline (Charness, 1988). However, not all cognitive skills are affected with aging, for example crystallised intelligence (like vocabulary) remains constant or improves over age. Fluid intelligence (such as problem-solving, learning, and pattern recognition abilities), on the other hand, declines markedly (Bäckman, Small, & Wahlin, 2001).

Recent studies on ageing and intuitive use of technological products concluded that older people are an diverse group and that technology prior-experience and cognitive functioning (central executive function in specific) are more relevant to fast and effective use of products than chronological age (Lewis, et al., 2008; Reddy, et al., 2010). The Central executive is an active component of the Working Memory system. It is a limited capacity system used for tasks that involve decision making, directing attention to relevant information, suppressing irrelevant information and allocating cognitive resources when performing more than one task simultaneously (Baddeley, 2002). Central executive function deteriorates with age and the effect of this decline becomes more pronounced as the complexity of cognitive tasks increases, such as when a task requires simultaneous storage and processing of information (Bäckman, et al., 2001).

OLDER ADULTS AND PRIOR-EXPERIENCE

The way people handle current technology could be based on the kind of technology they were exposed to during their formative years (10-25 years) (Sackmann & Weymann, 1994). People can be identified as belonging to a certain “technological generation” based on the kind of consumer products and technology that they were exposed to in their formative years (Docampo Rama, Ridder, & Bouma, 2001). Czaja (2006) suggest that a group of people belonging to a certain technological generation will find it hard to use devices from newer generations, mostly because they lack prior experience with related technology.

Prior experience with technology is a strong predictor of performance on a variety of computer-based tasks (Czaja, Sharit, Ownby, Roth, & Nair, 2001), such that the more experience a user has with related technology the faster they will learn to use newer ones (Lewis, et al., 2008). Recent empirical research on prior experience and usability of products found that interactions which exploit user’s prior-knowledge are significantly faster and are less prone to errors (Blackler, Popovic, et al., 2010; Langdon, Lewis, & Clarkson, 2007; Lawry, Blackler, & Popovic, 2010; Lewis, et al., 2008; Reddy, Blackler, Popovic, & Mahar, 2009). Furthermore, technology prior-experience (prior-experience with related technologies) is also an important factor in intuitive use of an interface (Blackler, Popovic, et al., 2010). However, ageing causes, at varying levels, decline in fluid intelligence (Bäckman, et al., 2001), which in turn slows down the acquisition of new knowledge. This could be one of the reasons why older adults find it difficult to use new technological products intuitively.

REDUNDANCY AND INTUITIVE USE

Some studies discovered that older users face difficulties in using interfaces that use graphics extensively (Gould & Schaefer, 2005). Graphics intensive interfaces can also increase extraneous cognitive load and can hamper learning of their functionality (Feinberg & Murphy, 2000; Sweller, 1994). It is suggested that using descriptive language

to define the function of a button could help in using an interface intuitively (Gould & Schaefer, 2005). Some researchers also hypothesised that older people might perform better with words than symbols (Blackler, 2008). This further suggests that redundancy in interfaces might help older people and users with low prior experience. Redundancy refers to a repetition of content in different format. The repetition has to be in an alternative physical form, for example, voice and text or picture and text (Wickens, Lee, Liu, & Becker, 2004). Furthermore, research from the field of instructional design suggests that redundancy of graphics and words is most beneficial to accommodate individual differences in cognitive abilities (Tindall-Ford, Chandler, & Sweller, 1997).

There is a considerable amount of research in the field of educational technology that suggests the use of multimodal representation to reduce the cognitive load for the learner. Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller, 1999) is one such outcome that is used extensively to inform the design of product's user interfaces. This theory focuses on efficient use of available cognitive processing for learning. Cognitive load can be described as the amount of working memory resources used at any point during the learning process. Sweller (2002) suggests that if information is presented in two modalities, for example audio and visual, demand on working memory is reduced. Research in cognitive psychology also indicated that more working memory is available when dual modalities (Auditory and Visual) are used (Penney, 1989).

Some interaction design research also suggests that redundant textual description that restates what is shown in a diagram is very beneficial for novices or learners with no prior knowledge. Furthermore, it could also help in making products more intuitive for people with degraded cognitive ability and people with low prior experience (Gould & Schaefer, 2005). On the other hand, redundancy is detrimental to users with high prior knowledge (Vetere & Howard, 2000). Sweller (2002) terms this as the "redundancy effect", which states that if one form of information representation is intelligible by itself, repeating it in another form will increase

cognitive processing load. For example, graphical interface with redundancy (Figure 1) is helpful for novice users to learn the function of this control, however, for expert users both forms of representation are intelligible, hence redundancy effect.

Figure 1: Redundant (text + symbol) representation of start function

In summary, some research indicates importance of redundancy in interface design, and some highlights negative aspects of redundancy. However, there is no data available that supports these suggestions in interface design context. This experiment was designed to investigate the impact of a Redundant interface design on its intuitive use, especially in older people.

ABOUT REDUNDANCY AND REPRESENTATION

Semiotics, in short, can be defined as a "study of sign" (Chandler, 2002). A sign is defined as something that represents or stands for something else. All signs are interpreted based on the prior-experience/convention. Convention means as convened, agreed upon, and accordingly shared in a given social context and culture (Nadin, 1988). A sign will acquire a meaning only when someone interprets it as signifying something other than itself (Chandler, 2002).

There are three types of signs, (1) Iconic representation: Direct relationship, (2) Indexic representation: by association, (3) Symbolic representation: by convention. Iconic and indexic representations are not possible for abstract concepts. For example, power switch can be represented indexically as 1/0; however, the symbols (1 and 0) cannot be deciphered with out the knowledge of binary system. A simple way to understand iconic and indexic representations would be, for example, an iconic representation for a tree would be a picture of a tree and an indexic representation could be a leaf or a branch.

In this paper the terms “Text/words”, “Symbols” are used in their colloquial sense. However, from a semiotics point of view both “Text/words” and “Symbol” are symbolic representations. As both are based on conventions, one is based on verbal language and the other visual language.

EXPERIMENT DESIGN

This experiment was designed to investigate the following research questions:

- Does redundancy novice (low/no prior experience) or older users with age-related cognitive degradation in using complex product interfaces intuitively?
- Is redundancy in interface design detrimental for expert users?
- What are the effects of ageing on time to complete the task, number of errors and intuitive uses?

The design of the experiment was based on studies investigating intuitive use conducted previously (Blackler, 2008). This experiment is a cross-sectional, between-groups matched-subject design. Participants for this experiment were recruited from different sources to maintain a good sample of the general population. Individuals from various organisations (sports clubs, educational institutes, recreational facilities and retirement resorts) were approached to ask if they could volunteer to take part in this study. Overall 58 participants participated in this study of which data from 44 participants was analysed. Of 44 participants 41% were males and 59% females, ages ranging from 18 to 83 years ($M = 54$, $SD = 19.6$). The data from the remaining 14 participants was not included as 11 of them were part of the pilot study and 3 were suspected to be suffering from severe cognitive decline.

VARIABLES, METHODS AND MEASUREMENT TOOLS

The Dependent variables for this experiment were time to complete the tasks, the percentage of intuitive correct uses and the number of errors. The

Independent variables and their levels are listed in Table 1.

Independent variables	Levels of Independent variables
Interface design	Words only
	Symbols only
	Redundant (text and symbols)
Age groups	17 to 34 years
	35 to 49 years
	50 to 64 years
	65 to 72 years
	73+ years

Table 1: Independent variables and their levels, 3X5X2 factorial design

NOTE ON AGE GROUPS

Age groups were allocated purely for the statistical analysis. However, as can be seen in Table 1, not all age ranges are equal. The reason for this is that older people are more diverse in their capabilities than younger people. We tried to resolve this by keeping age variations in older groups much narrower than younger age groups. In general, data indicates that increasing the number of age groups will address the variability within a group much more effectively, especially for participants above 65 years. However, from a “statistical power” point of view, this will also makes it necessary to increase number of participants in each group to sizes that is not feasible for given time span of this study. In this paper all the data that involves interaction design uses 5 age groups for ANOVA. The data from cognitive measures uses 3 age groups mostly to make the correlation charts easier to read.

DATA COLLECTION METHODS

This research used multiple data collection methods. These are verbal protocol, observation of task performance, rating scale questionnaire and cognitive measures tasks.

VERBAL PROTOCOL, OBSERVATION OF TASK PERFORMANCE

Two cameras were used to record the experiment (Figure 3). The audio-visual recording was subsequently coded and analysed using Noldus Observer (Noldus, Trienes, Hendriksen, Jansen, &

Jansen, 2000). Noldus Observer is a software that helps in coding the data from the video recordings such as.

RATING SCALE QUESTIONNAIRE

The technology prior-experience questionnaire, based on previous Technology Familiarity questionnaire (Blackler, 2008), was administered in two stages to avoid priming effect. Priming is the implicit memory effect in which prior exposure to a stimulus influences retrieval/recognition accuracy of subsequent stimulus (Neely, 1991). The first part of the questionnaire was administered before the trial (containing questions that are not directly related to the product used for the trial) and the second part after the trials (this part had questions that are directly related to the product used in the trials).

COGNITIVE MEASURES TASKS

The cognitive measures software is an interactive application developed by us (Blackler, Mahar, & Popovic, 2010; Reddy, et al., 2010) that administers various instruments that measure different aspects of cognitive function. For this experiment the following five instruments were used:

(1 and 2). Corsi-span and Digit-span: Measures visual sketchpad and phonological loop capacity. A standard Corsi Span task was used where participants viewed sets of squares on the screen, recalled their locations by button click. The number of squares presented was varied using a staircase procedure to find the participants visual span. Similarly, Digit Span was measured by presenting lists of digits one at a time on the screen. Participants recalled the lists by clicking on a number pad on the screen. Again a staircase procedure was used to vary the list length.

(3 and 4). Visual and Phonological transform task: Measure of Central Executive capacity to manipulate spatial and phonological information. In the Phonological transform task participants viewed a set of 4 numbers then were required to move each number forward by 4 places (e.g. 5 would become 9). Similarly, in Visual transform task participants viewed a pattern of 4 dots on a disk then were

required to rotate them 4 places in clockwise direction.

(5). Go/No-Go task: Sustained attention and response inhibition. This instrument was also used to measure Choice Reaction Time of participants. In the Go/No-go task (Nielson, Langenecker, & Garavan, 2002) participants viewed individual letters serially on the screen and were required to respond to stipulated targets. There were 3 sets of trials in this task. First set: they were required to respond, by clicking a button, when ever they saw specific letters (X,Y and Z), second set: they were required to respond to only alternating target letters X and Y. For example, if they clicked on X in one instance they should only respond when they see Y (X, Y, X, Y). And in the third set: participants were required to respond to three alternating target letters (X, Y, X, Z, Y, Z).

The data from Noldus Observer, Technology prior-experience questionnaires and Cognitive Measures software were exported into SPSS for statistical analysis.

DATA ANALYSIS

Keeping in view the nature of this study, in terms of complex and rich data derived from multiple methods of data collection, it was felt that it is best this research takes a quantitative approach. The dependent variables “time on task”, “number of intuitive uses” and “errors” are central to this experiment. Time on task is an important indicator of intuitive use. Intuitive interaction is fast and generally non-conscious and people would often be unable to explain how they made decisions during intuitive interaction (Blackler, 2008, p. 107). Time on tasks and errors are relatively easy to measure. On the other hand, collecting data on actions that are non-conscious is much more challenging. As intuitive use is non-conscious, often participants don’t verbalise intuitive actions during concurrent protocol delivery. Data on intuitive use is acquired based on observations in conjunction with verbal protocol using Noldus Observer software. When participants performed an action fast, with ease and did not verbalise (or at times verbalised after,

instead of while, performing the action) that interaction was coded as an intuitive use.

APPARATUS AND MEASURES

This experiment used a commercially available body fat analyser as product mediator. This device was selected after carefully reviewing other over-the-counter health monitoring devices, including blood pressure, glucose and cholesterol monitors. The decision to use the body fat analyser was primarily based on the assumption that this product provides enough interest for both younger and older participants. Hawthorn (2007) suggests that a test product should be perceived as useful to sufficiently motivate the participants to engage them in the experiment.

For the actual experiment a virtual version of the product was used, as it was not possible to modify the physical device to test the “Interface” independent variable. The virtual product was an Adobe Flash based application that was used on a touch sensitive LCD monitor (Figure 2, Figure 3a,). The virtual product application allows the researcher to setup it up individually for every participant.

Figure 2: Virtual body fat analyser device with modified interface and controls to represent Redundant interface

The setup function is used to alter the default number shown on the device for age, height and weight. This is done to make sure no matter what the age, weight or height of the participants they were always required to perform the same number of actions to complete the task. For example, if the participant’s age was 83 years, he/she would see the default number as 68 (15 less than the participants age). If the participant’s age was 45 years, he/she would see 30 as default value. This is done to ensure that all participants require the same number of

actions to complete the task to avoid influencing the dependent variable time on task.

Figure 3: Experiment setup with virtual device on touch screen monitor (a) overall setup, (b) face camera view and (c) screen camera view.

Two cameras were used to record the experiment (Figure 3a) for later analysis using Noldus Observer software. One camera was positioned to record participant’s facial expressions and body language (Figure 3b); and the second camera was positioned to record the tasks performed by the participant on the screen (Figure 3c).

PROCEDURE

This experiment was conducted in a controlled laboratory setting. The whole experiment was scripted to ensure consistency between participants. Participants were first given an information package that explained what the experiment was about, and what it meant to participate in it. Once they understood the content of the package and had no doubts about their participation in the experiment, they were asked to sign the consent form. Then they were shown around the laboratory and the experiment setup was explained. Participants were also informed that they could stop the experiment at any time and request to delete all the records of their participation. The whole experiment took roughly 70 minutes. The protocol of the experiment involves three broad stages.

1. Pre-trials: Information package and consent form signing (including permission to use their

pictures in research publications), eye acuity testing, Technology prior-experience questionnaire part-I.

2. **Trials:** Task 1 involved switching on the device, inputting necessary details (age, gender, weight and height) and saving the data followed by instructing the device to measure and display body fat mass and volume. Task 2 involved switching the device on, recalling saved data, updating the data and instructing the device to measure and display body fat mass and volume. Participants were informed that, if they were not comfortable to divulge their personal information, they could provide false, but realistic, data. They were also informed that help would be provided on request if they were unable to complete a task after repeated attempts.
3. **Post-trials:** Technology prior-experience questionnaire part-II, and cognitive measures interactive tasks.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results suggest that a negative correlation exist between technology prior experience and time to complete the task, $r(43) = -.482, p .001$ (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Time taken to complete the task, technology prior experience and age group differences.

Younger people also tended to score higher on technology prior-experience and were more likely to use interfaces faster than older people.

Figure 5: Box plots for time on task by 3 age groups

As can be seen in Figure 5 the variability in time to complete the task increases with age, with the younger group being more homogeneous than the older age group. An analysis of variance showed a main effect of Age on time to complete task was significant, $F(2, 40) = 21.3, P < .001, \eta_p^2 = .516$.

However, contrary to prediction, participants with mid and low technology prior-experience took more time to complete tasks on the Redundant interface (text and symbol) than did those on the Words only interface (Figure 6). On the other hand, participants with high technology prior-experience were faster on the Redundant interface than the Words only interface. All three groups took most time to complete the task on Symbols only interface. An 3x3 ANOVA with interface types (Words only, Symbols only, Redundant) and technology prior-experience levels (Low, Mid, High) was used to test differences between means for significance. Figure 6 shows the mean time to complete the task as a function of technology prior-experience and type of interface.

It is evident from Figure 6 that, people with mid and high technology prior-experience performed significantly better than people with low technology prior-experience, $F(2, 35) = 7.3, p = .002, \eta_p^2 = 0.296$ and the interface type also has significant impact on time to complete the task, $F(2, 35) = 3.9, p = .029$,

$\eta_p^2 = .183$. The interaction effect between interface and technology prior-experience was not significant, $F(4, 35) = 0.412, p = .80, \eta_p^2 = .045$.

Figure 6: Technology prior-experience and interfaces

An 3x5 ANOVA with interface types (Words only, Symbols only, Redundant) and Age groups (17 to 34, 35 to 49, 50 to 64, 65 to 72 and 73+ years) was used to test differences between means for significance. Figure 7 shows the mean time to complete the task as a function of age and type of interface. An inspection of Figure 7 reveals that the effect of age was much larger for the redundant and Symbols only interface than it was for the Words only interface. The difference was reflected in a significant Age x Type of interface interaction, $F(8, 29) = 3.55, p = .005, \eta_p^2 = .0495$. It is also evident from Figure 7 that, overall, the younger age group performed better than older age group, $F(4, 29) = 17.4, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.706$ and type of interface also has significant impact on time to complete the task $F(2, 29) = 17.8, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = .552$.

An analysis of simple effects showed there was significant age differences in interface type symbols, $F(4,29) = 18, p < .001$, and redundant $F(4,29) = 9.34, p < .001$. However, for interface level words there is no significant age differences, $F(4,29) = 1.2, p = .221$.

Figure 7: Time to complete task, age groups and interface level

Figure 7 clearly shows that younger participants (below 65) took the least amount of time on Redundant interface followed by Words only and Symbols only interface. However, contrary to what was hypothesised, older participants (65+) were significantly faster on the Words only interface when compared to the Redundant interface.

Figure 8: Errors, Age groups and interfaces

Older people also made more errors on the Redundant interface when compared with Words only interface (Figure 8). An 3x5 ANOVA with

interface levels (Words only, Symbols only, Redundant) and age levels (17 to 34, 35 to 49, 50 to 64, 65 to 72 and 73+ years) as between-subjects factors revealed main effects of interface, $F(2, 29) = 11.6, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = .444$, and age, $F(4, 29) = 5.08, p = .003, \eta_p^2 = 0.412$. The interaction effect between interface and age was not significant, $F(8, 29) = 1.512, p = .196, \eta_p^2 = .294$. However, the large effect size suggests that there is an effect but as F is not significant it can't be said that there is an interaction. On the other hand, another study with more power could possibly find an interaction.

Younger people also used the interface more intuitively than older people (Figure 9). They were fastest and most intuitive on the Redundant interface. The trend changes with age, older people used the interfaces less intuitively and also found Words only interface more intuitive to use.

Figure 9: Intuitive use, Age groups and interfaces

An 3x5 ANOVA with interface levels (Words only, Symbols only, Redundant) and Age levels (17 to 34, 35 to 49, 50 to 64, 65 to 72 and 73+ years) as between-subjects factors revealed a main effects of Interface, $F(2, 29) = 4.4, p < .022, \eta_p^2 = .232$, and Age, $F(4, 29) = 0.62, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.570$. The interaction effect between Interface and Age was not significant, $F(8, 29) = .575, p = .790, \eta_p^2 = .137$. Here again the effect size is large however the experiment lacked power to detect it.

Figure 10: Error recovery with help, Age groups and interfaces.

An 3x5 ANOVA with interface levels (Words only, Symbols only, Redundant) and Age levels (17 to 34, 35 to 49, 50 to 64, 65 to 72 and 73+ years) as between-subjects factors revealed main effects of Interface, $F(2, 18) = 11.3, p = .001, \eta_p^2 = .557$, and Age groups, $F(4, 18) = 9.5, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.679$. However, the interaction effect was significant, $F(8, 18) = 1.12, p = .006, \eta_p^2 = .647$.

As shown in Figure 10, older participants (65+) needed most help in recovering from errors and completing the task successfully. They received most help on the Symbols only interface followed by Redundant interface. On the other hand younger participants (below 65) needed least help on the Redundant interface followed by words and Symbols only interface. For interface level Symbols, $F(4, 18) = 18.2, p < .001$, and Redundant, $F(4, 18) = 4.56, p = .01$, the age effect was significant. However, for interface level words there is no significant Age effect, $F(4, 18) = .24, p = .932$.

COGNITIVE MEASURES DATA

The data from this experiment shows a strong negative correlation between sustained attention, time on task, $r(43) = -.402, p = .007$ (Figure 11) and the number of errors, $r(43) = -.318, p < .05$ (Figure 12).

Age was also negatively correlated with Sustained attention $r(43) = -.454, p = .002$.

Figure 11: Sustained attention, age and time to complete the task.

Figure 12: Sustained attention, age and number of errors

Some recent research suggested correlation between Central Executive functions and time on task (Blackler, Mahar, et al., 2010; Lewis, et al., 2008; Lewis, Langdon, & Clarkson, 2006; Reddy, et al., 2010). As the Central Executive function plays a key role in controlling and directing attention (Morrison, 2005) this data not only supports existing research but also goes further in identifying one of its subcomponents specifically. Further more, there is also a strong correlation between sustained attention and the amount of explicit help received to recover from the errors, $r(43) = -.409, p < .05$.

There was also a significant negative correlation between Visual sketchpad capacity and time on task, $r(43) = -.431, p .004$ (Figure 13). This could be due to the visual nature of the product interface used in the trials. Jenkins, Myerson, Joerding, and Hale (2000) suggests ageing adversely affects visuospatial information processing more than verbal information processing. They also reported that older adults are slower when processing visuospatial information compared with verbal information. Ageing also affects memory for spatial information more than verbal information. Furthermore, they also suggest that older people find it more difficult to cope with novel visiospatial information than novel verbal information. This provides an explanation for older people taking more time on Redundant interfaces. In a Redundant interface the amount of information to process is twice that of Words only.

Figure 13: Visual sketchpad capacity and time on task.

Processing-speed Theory, proposed by Salthouse (1996), suggests that ageing causes a slowing down of processing speed. However, if older people were allowed more time on the task, the performance differences between young and old would be minimal.

The data from this study suggests a strong correlation between Choice Reaction time and time to complete the task, $r(42) = .376, p = .012$ and

between age and Choice Reaction Time $r(42) = .523$, $p < .001$ (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Choice reaction time and time on task.

However, contrary to Processing-speed Theory, even though there was no time restriction to complete the task, older participants were slower and made more errors than younger participants. However, as can be seen from Table 2, there is lot more variability in older participants.

Condition	Mean	SD
18 to 40 years	2.08	1.7
41 to 65 years	3.6	1.7
65+ years	5.4	2.7

Table 2: Means and Standard Deviations of the number of errors by age group conditions

On the other hand, there are other variables that correlate to errors. For example, there is a negative correlation between technology prior-experience and errors, $r(42) = -.287$, $p = .06$.

It was also observed that, when compared with younger people, the older people took more time to recover from mistakes and also tended to get more anxious when the task got difficult. Both of these issues will be further investigated in our next set of experiments.

CONCLUSION

This study was designed to investigate if redundancy in product interface design facilitates intuitive use

of complex products in older people and people with low technology prior-experience. The study involved participation of people of ages from 18 to 83. The results of this study suggest a strong correlation between technology prior-experience and time to complete the task. Furthermore, contrary to what was expected, older people (65+ years) completed the tasks on the Words only based interface significantly faster than on the Redundant interface. The rest of the participants, as expected, completed tasks significantly faster on the Redundant interface. From a cognitive processing perspective, as anticipated, the Central Executive function (a component of Working Memory) has emerged as one of the important cognitive functions in using complex interfaces. The strongest negative correlations were observed between sustained attention (one of the functions of the Central Executive), and both the time to complete the task and the number of errors made by the participants. The significance of this study is that it clearly establishes age differences and reasons behind them on using complex product interfaces.

From an interaction design perspective, this research suggests that interfaces that put minimal load on Working Memory would be beneficial for older people. For example, deep nested (multi-layered) interfaces should be avoided. Findings also suggest a Redundant interface (text and symbols) requires more working memory resources and should be avoided for older users. Instead using simple descriptive text based interfaces would be more beneficial. Overall, keeping the interfaces clean and simple with minimal distractions to reduce use of limited attention resources may be most helpful for older users.

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